
From Debt to Donations: Impact of Capital Structure on Risk and Return in Microfinance Institutions

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Abstract

This study investigates the impact of capital structure on the risk and return of microfinance institutions (MFIs) in Bangladesh by analyzing the yearly data of 61 MFIs from 2012 to 2023. Four capital structure components, i.e., the Grameen model, quasi-equity, debt, & philanthropic funds, are used in this study. Here, the portfolio yield and operating self-sufficiency are used as proxies of the return of MFIs, and the loan-to-deposit ratio is used as the proxy of the risk measure of MFIs. Moreover, the average loan size of MFIs is also used as the control variable, which measures the outreach of clients of MFIs. Panel data analysis is conducted utilizing the FGLS model, and the robustness of the results of the FGLS model is checked by performing the random effect model. The findings suggest that most capital structure elements adversely impact the returns of MFIs, except for the Grameen model, which has an insignificant correlation with returns. In contrast, the components of capital structure substantially raise the risk of MFIs, except Philanthropic funds, which exert an insignificant impact. The findings highlight the influence of capital structure on MFI performance, indicating that higher amounts of quasi-equity and debt diminish returns and amplify risk due to financial costs and adverse effects of leverage. The Grameen model's weak association with returns implies modest profitability effects, and the minimal impact of philanthropic funds on risk denotes that donations slightly influence financial stability. Microfinance institutions should strategically balance funding sources to improve financial sustainability while minimizing risk.

Keywords: *Microfinance Institutions, Portfolio Yield, Operating Self-Sufficiency, Grameen Model, Quasi-Equity and Philanthropic Fund*

JEL Code: *G21, G32, O16, D64, L31*

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INTRODUCTION

Microcredit policies have been implemented to provide financial services to the marginal population who are often excluded from the traditional banking systems. Microfinance institutions (MFIs) have come up with microcredit services such as saving facilities, microloans, and insurance products to alleviate poverty, and economic and sustainable development by providing loans without collateral or at a very low interest rate (Nelson & Peter, 2019; Tria, Harun & Alam, 2022). The capital structure of MFIs is related to sustainable returns and managing risks; therefore, the long-term viability and effectiveness of MFIs depend crucially on the structure of capital. Given the significant operational variability of MFIs, it is crucial to identify how the components of capital structure affect risk and return, drawing on theories such as the Modigliani-Miller proposition, trade-off theory, and pecking order theory.

The capital structure of MFIs exhibits significant diversity, which comprises a substantial combination of the Grameen model, quasi-equity, debt, and philanthropic funds (Mia, Ahmed, & Nomon, 2021). This unique type of capital structure component affects the financial and operational performance of MFIs, specifically the risk and return (Berk & DeMarzo, 2007; D'Espallier, Hudon & Szafarz, 2013). Previous studies (e.g., Islam & Nasreen, 2018; Mia et al., 2021; Parvin, Hossain, Mohiuddin & Cao, 2020) have examined the volume of capital structure and its impact on return, but little is known about its impact on risk. Empirical evidence on the impact of different capital structure components on the risk and return of MFIs is limited, especially in Bangladesh. Therefore, this study addresses this gap by examining the effect of four capital structure components (Grameen model, quasi-equity, debt, and philanthropic funds) on the risk, measured by loan-to-deposit ratio, and return, measured by portfolio yield and operational self-sufficiency, of MFIs in Bangladesh. To reach the research objective, a total of 732 observations for each capital structure

component, along with the risk and return measures, have been collected from 61 MFIs operated in Bangladesh.

LITERATURE REVIEW AND HYPOTHESES DEVELOPMENT

Microfinance institutions (MFIs) build capital structures to balance two objectives, which are the financial sustainability of MFIs and social impact (Dube & Kwenda, 2023), unlike traditional financial institutions that organize their capital to optimize value and reduce expenses. The capital structure of traditional firms is defined as the composition of accumulated capital from different sources, especially debt and equity (Myers & Majluf, 1984; Rajan & Zingales, 1995). However, the main sources of capital of MFIs in Bangladesh are clients' savings or deposits; loans from Palli Karma Sahayak Foundation (PKSF), governments, commercial banks, and other MFIs; donors' funds and cumulative surplus, which have their unique features (Islam, 2021). These sources of funds are further categorized as the Grameen model, quasi-equity, debt and philanthropic funds (Mia et al., 2021), which is shown in Figure 1.

Notes: This figure shows the capital structure components following the Microfinance Regulatory Authority (MRA) guidelines, which are aligned with Mia et al. (2021).

Figure 1: Capital structure components of MFIs in Bangladesh

The Grameen model of financing in the capital structure emphasizes social impact and financial sustainability and relies heavily on clients' deposits and cumulative surplus (Hoque, Chishty, & Halloway, 2011). Mia et al. (2021) classify soft loans—including PKSF loans, government money, peer borrowing from other MFIs, subsidies, and donations—as quasi-equity, signifying a combination of debt and equity financing. Credits from commercial banks, regarded as debt in the capital structure, can facilitate the expansion of MFIs' operational activities but frequently elevate financial leverage and repayment responsibilities, thus amplifying risk exposure (Pagano, 2005). Lastly, Philanthropic funds, derived from donations or charity contributions, are essential for promoting social agendas; however, they do not always ensure financial independence.

Several theories, such as Modigliani and Miller's theory (Modigliani & Miller, 1958), trade-off theory (Myers 1984), and pecking order theory (Myers and Majluf, 1984), have been developed over time to discuss the relationship between capital structure and the risk and return of a firm. The Modigliani-Miller propositions discuss the connection between capital construction, firm worth, and the risk and return of a firm (Modigliani & Miller, 1958; Modigliani & Miller, 1963). Assuming a perfect capital market, Modigliani and Miller's theory contends that a firm's value is unaffected by its capital structure, as investors can reproduce leverage effects within their portfolios (Berk & DeMarzo, 2007; Kyereboah-Coleman, 2007). Nonetheless, considering the imperfections in the MFI market, including elements like taxation, bankruptcy expenses, and agency fees, the capital structure choices of MFIs may substantially influence their risk and return, contrary to the Modigliani-Miller theorem. Modigliani and Miller's theorem shaped trade-off and pecking order theories' development (Pagano, 2005). The trade-off hypothesis asserts that corporations create an optimal capital structure by weighing the tax advantages of debt against the costs of financial crises and agency issues. This idea is especially pertinent for MFIs, which frequently encounter significant operational risks due to their social objectives and providing loans to a low-income customer base without collateral (Pagano, 2005). The trade-off argument suggests that while modest debt might improve returns via tax benefits, excessive debt may heighten financial risk (Myers 1984). The Pecking Order Theory (Myers and Majluf, 1984) clarifies capital structure decisions by indicating that organizations favour internal financing to minimize information asymmetry, utilizing debt only when essential and equity as a final alternative. This paradigm is especially pertinent for MFIs, which frequently encounter restricted access to external capital and emphasize financial sustainability. MFIs choose debt

over stock to avoid dilution and associated costs while accumulating the funding, even though more debt can raise financial risk. Figure 2 shows the conceptual framework by integrating these theoretical perspectives to explore how capital structure components affect the risk and return of MFIs.

Source: Author's Own Work

Figure 2: Conceptual framework integrating theoretical perspectives of the relationship between the capital structure component with the risk and return

MFIs promote financial and socio-economic development by providing micro-loans to individuals and small businesses such as cottage, micro, small, and medium enterprises (CMSME), activating business ventures and revenue creation (Khandker, 2005). Capital structure has been found essential in the sustainability of microfinance institutions (Sekabira, 2013). Different compositions of capital sources lead to different outcomes on the financial performance and sustainability of MFIs (Dabi, Nugraha, Disman & Sari, 2023). The main sources of revenue for the microfinance institutions are interest on provided small loans, yield from investments in low-risk-environments, service fees charged on MFI products like loan service and insurance service, and other grants and subsidies (Armendariz & Morduch, 2010;

Mersland & Strøm, 2009; Ledgerwood, 1998; Hermes, & Lensink, 2007). Although MFIs are loosely NGO-based organizations, their operation should be profitable to sustain in the long run.

Previous studies (e.g., Tadele, Roberts, & Whiting, 2018; Geresem & Michael, 2021) create debate regarding the effect of the capital structure on risk and return. For example, Hăpău (2018) and Rutanga, Barayandema, & Mutarindwa (2021) opined that equity positively impacts the operating performance of a MFIs, which means that a higher ratio of equity capital in comparison to total assets leads to better MFI performance. Equity, interchangeably with the Grameen model, has a positive impact on risk and return in the context of Bangladesh (Parvin et al., 2020; Islam & Nasreen, 2018). Conversely, Hoque et al. (2011) found that higher equity capital lowers the firm performance. Geresem and Michael (2021) conducted studies on Uganda and found that capital structure has no significant impact on performance in terms of risk and return of MFIs.

In the case of debt, Kar (2012) and Bibi, Raza & Javid (2022) opined that an increase in debt is positively related to financial self-sufficiency and profit efficiency by lowering the cost and tax savings. Debt impacts performance positively as the ratio of total debt to total asset, long-term debt to total asset and short-term debt to asset positively affects the cost of financing (Kyereboah-Coleman, 2007). In the context of Bangladesh, higher leverage improves the performance of MFIs (Islam & Nasreen, 2018). However, Parvin et al. (2020) and Sekabira (2013) opined that debt creates a negative impact on the operating profitability of MFIs. Extensive use of commercial loans diminishes the efficiency of MFIs because it raises loan costs (Hoque et al., 2011). Furthermore, Dang, Linh, Nguyen, and Hoang (2023) stated that MFIs with higher debt in the capital composition face higher regulatory, liquidity, and credit risk, and thus, debt reduces financial self-sufficiency (Rutanga et al., 2021). Moreover, Almansour, Alrawashdeh, and Almansour (2019) found no impact of debt on performance.

Donations are the portion of capital that comes from charitable sources. Donations are significantly negatively associated with MFI's cost per borrower, thus increasing performance (Bibi et al., 2022). Bogan (2012) argued that higher extent use of grants by giant MFIs decreases operational self-sufficiency. Sekabira (2013) found a negative correlation between grants and operational as well as financial sustainability. In Bangladesh, donations have not contributed significantly to micro-finance institutions' risk-return characteristics (Islam & Nasreen, 2018).

Risk is another component of the measure of performance of MIFs. The MFIs face risks due to internal and external factors, requiring robust risk management practices to protect their financial stability and sustainability (Sekabira, 2013; Kar, 2012). The key risks of MFIs are credit risk, liquidity risk, operational risk, regulatory risk, and outside shocks (Bibi et al., 2022; Khachatryan, Hartarska & Grigoryan, 2017). Parvin et al. (2020) found that the equity-to-asset ratio and debt-to-loan ratio significantly impact the risk of microfinance institutions in Bangladesh. An ideal capital design can assist with alleviating liquidity risk in MFIs. It also revealed that more elevated levels of debt in MFIs can worsen liquidity risk, as extreme debt obligation might strain incomes (Mersland & Strøm, 2009). Moreover, higher borrowing cost raises the default ratio and lessens the productivity of MFIs (Dang et al., 2023). In contrast, Dabi et al. (2023) and Almansour et al. (2019) found that capital structure has no significant impact on the risk of MFIs.

Average loan size measures the depth of outreach of the microfinance institutions (Kar, 2012; Mia et al., 2021). It exhibits the extent of loans disbursed to the clients and borrowers and the loan size influences the revenue and risk of MFIs (Parvin et al., 2020). Average loan size is mainly used as the control variable, one of the microeconomic parameters of MFIs, to justify the impact of capital construction on their risk and return (Chauhan, Kumar, & Verma, 2024).

The majority of the studies (Hăpău, 2018; Rutanga et al., 2021; Bogan, 2012; Chauhan et al., 2024) have focused on ratios like equity-to-asset ratio, debt-to-total assets and debt-to-equity ratio as proxies of capital structure, ignoring the four major components of capital structure, such as the Grameen model, quasi-equity, debt and philanthropic funds of MFIs. A few studies, like Islam and Nasreen (2018), Mia et al. (2021), and Parvin et al. (2020), incorporated major capital structure components of MFIs. However, a comprehensive analysis of capital structure components' impact on performance, including the return, measured by portfolio yield, operating self-sufficiency, and liquidity, and risk measured by loan-to-deposit ratio, remains limited in the context of Bangladesh. Furthermore, the contribution of firm-specific factors like average loan size as a control variable remains undiscovered while analyzing the impact of capital structure on microfinance institution's risk and return.

Therefore, this study aims to fill the gap by exploring the influence of capital structure on the risk and return of MFIs in Bangladesh, where data from 61 Bangladeshi MFIs spanning from 2012 to 2023 are utilized. To reach the objective of the research, the following

hypotheses are made for identifying the impact of capital structure on the risk and returns of MFIs:

H1 = Capital structure has a significant impact on the return of the MFIs.

H2 = Capital structure significantly impacts the risk of the MFIs.

DATA AND METHODOLOGY

The data have been collected from the annual report of 61 MFIs and the Microfinance Regulatory Authority (MRA)¹ from 2012 to 2023. Initially, 80 MFIs of Bangladesh were selected; however, to reduce the outlier in the dataset and make a balanced panel dataset, 19 firms were deducted from the initial sample. Hasan, Islam, Tawfiq, and Saha (2025) opined that a balanced dataset reduces the biases of results; this research selects a sample of 61 MFIs in Bangladesh. Four components of capital structure of MFIs have been used in this study like the Grameen model (Mia et al., 2021; Anggreni & Rahyuda, 2021), quasi-equity (Bogan, 2012; Dabi et al., 2023), debt (Chauhan et al., 2020; Parvin et al., 2020), and philanthropic funds (Khachatryan et al., 2017; Tadele et al., 2018).

Here, the portfolio yield following Chauhan et al. (2024), Hasan & Islam (2022), Hăpău (2018), and Sekabira (2013) and operating self-sufficiency following Dab et al. (2023), Chauhan et al. (2024), Nelson and Peter (2019), Rutanga et al. (2021) Bogan (2012) and Dabi et al. (2023) have been utilized as the proxies of return measures of MFIs. Moreover, the loan-to-deposit ratio has been selected as the proxy of risk measurement following Anggreni and Rahyuda (2021), Duho, Duho, and Forson (2021), Sari and Murni (2016) and Parvin et al. (2020). In addition, the average loan size is utilized as the control variable in this study because it serves as an indicator of the extent of MFIs clients that concurrently affect the revenue and risk profiles of MFIs (Kar, 2012; Mia et al., 2021; Parvin et al., 2020). Brief discussions on variables are given in Table 1.

¹ <https://mra.gov.bd/>

Table 1: Variable Description

Serial No.	Variable Name	Variable Definition	References
Dependent Variables (Risk and Return measures)			
1	Portfolio yield	Portfolio yield (PY) measures the profit level in terms of relevant investment level or accumulated capital. The formula is as follows- $PY = \frac{\text{Total Interest Income}}{\text{Average Loan Outstanding}} * 100$	Chauhan et al. (2024); Hăpău (2018); Sekabira (2013)
2	Operating Self-sufficiency	Operating self-sufficiency (OSS) refers to the ability to make payments for operating costs with own generated revenues. The formula is as follows- $OSS = \frac{\text{Financial Income}}{\text{Financial Expenses} + \text{Administrative Cost} + \text{Loan Loss Provision}} * 100$	Bogan (2012); Dabi, et al. (2023)
3	Loan to Deposit ratio	The loan deposit ratio (LDR) calculates the proportion of disbursed loans in terms of total deposits within a firm. The formula is as follows- $LDR = \frac{\text{Total Loan}}{\text{Total Deposit}} * 100$	Sari and Murni (2016); Parvin et al., (2020)
Independent Variables (Components of Capital)			
4	Grameen Model	Grameen Model (GM) consists of client savings and cumulative surplus of retained earnings of the MFIs. The formula is- $GM = \text{Clients' Savings} + \text{Cumulative Surplus}$	Hoque et al. (2011); Anggreni and Rahyuda (2021)
5	Quasi Equity	Quasi equity (QE) consists of a loan from the Palli Karma-Sahayak Foundation (PKSF), the government, and other MFIs and donor's fund. The formula is- $QE = \text{Loans from PKSF} + \text{Loan from Government} + \text{Loan from other MFIs} + \text{Donor's Fund}$	Sekabira (2013); Bogan (2012); Dabi et al. (2023)
6	Debt	Debts are loans obtained from commercial banks.	Chauhan et al. (2020); Anggreni and Rahyuda (2021)
7	Philanthropic Funds	Philanthropic funds consist of other occasional loans and funds from charity and donations.	Khachatryan et al. (2017); Sekabira (2013)
Control Variables (Company Specific Factors)			
8	Average Loan Size	It is the natural logarithm of the total loan of MFIs that is provided to clients and measures the outreach depth.	Kar (2012); Bibi, Raza & Javid (2022)

In this study, the panel data analysis method is used following Hasan, Tawfiq, Hasan & Islam (2024a) and Hasan & Hasan (2024) because data contains both a time dimension, i.e., year, and cross-sectional dimension, which is MFIs. The three sets of regression equations below have been developed to assess the impact of capital structures on the return and risk level of microfinance institutions operating in Bangladesh. -

$$PY_{i,t} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 GM_{i,t} + \beta_2 QE_{i,t} + \beta_3 DE_{i,t} + \beta_4 PF_{i,t} + \beta_5 ALS_{i,t} + \varepsilon \dots \dots \dots (i)$$

$$OSS_{i,t} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 GM_{i,t} + \beta_2 QE_{i,t} + \beta_3 DE_{i,t} + \beta_4 PF_{i,t} + \beta_5 ALS_{i,t} + \varepsilon \dots \dots \dots (ii)$$

$$LDR_{i,t} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 GM_{i,t} + \beta_2 QE_{i,t} + \beta_3 DE_{i,t} + \beta_4 PF_{i,t} + \beta_5 ALS_{i,t} + \varepsilon \dots \dots \dots (iii)$$

Where *PY* represents portfolio yield, *OSS* stands for operating self-sufficiency, and *LDR* stands for loan-deposit ratio. Also, *i* stand for microfinance institutions, *t* is time, β is coefficients, *GM* is Grameen model, *QE* is quasi-equity, *DE* is debt, *PF* is philanthropic funds, and *ALS* is average loan size and ε is the error term of the regression.

RESULTS

Table 2 shows the descriptive statistics for all the selected variables. The mean value of portfolio yield is 19.88%, and the standard deviation is 6.44, indicating variability in income generation from loan portfolios. These results are slightly higher than the MFIs of India after the 2007 financial crisis (Chauhan et al., 2024). The average operating self-sufficiency is 106.58%, with a standard deviation of 29.98, which suggests that MFIs in Bangladesh have gained operational sustainability to cover the cost. Dabi et al. (2023) found similar operating self-sufficiency in Ghana. The loan-to-deposit ratio has a mean value of 2.18%, explaining that MFIs give away all their deposits as loans and rely on external funding to provide loans, which is aligned with Sari and Murni (2016) and Anggreni and Rahyuda (2021). Regarding the funding source, the Grameen Model has a mean value of BDT 2.52 crore, while the mean values of both quasi-equity and debt are BDT 1.16 crore, and the philanthropic fund is BDT 1.10 crore. It indicates that the portion of the Grameen Model in the capital structure is higher than all the other capital components, which is supported by Mia et al. (2021). Lastly, the logarithmic mean and standard deviation of average loan size are BDT 1.004 crore and 1.39, respectively, indicating substantial inconsistency in loan size among the MFIs. Here, the logarithmic minimum value of -3.20 crore signifies that MIFs provide small or less than 1

crore loan amounts; numerous MFIs distribute small loans to low-income customers which is consistent with their financial inclusion objectives.

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics

Variable	Obs.	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min.	Max.
Portfolio Yield (%)	732	19.88	6.44	0	39.35
Operating Self-Sufficiency (%)	732	106.58	29.98	16.38	196.57
Loan to Deposit Ratio (%)	732	3.18	2.54	0.05	35.65
Grameen Model (Crore)	732	2.52	3.01	-6.56	14.39
Quasi Equity (Crore)	732	1.16	2.13	0	11.31
Debt (Crore)	732	1.16	2.22	0	17.17
Philanthropic Fund (Crore)	732	1.10	2.19	0	18.03
Average Loan Size (Crore)	732	1.004	1.39	-3.20	5.20

Notes: The table presents descriptive statistics for examined variables, including the number of observations, mean, standard deviation, minimum, and maximum values of 80 Microfinance Institutes across Bangladesh from 2012 to 2023. Here, the portfolio yield, and operating self-sufficiency were used as return measures, loan to deposit ratio was used as risk measures and the Grameen model, quasi-equity, debt and philanthropic funds were used as capital structure. However, the logarithmic value of average loan size is considered a control variable. The rest of the variables are normalized using the inverse document frequency (IDF) method (Hasan & Hasan, 2024).

Table 3 presents the correlation matrix, exhibiting the pairwise relationships between variables. Here, the portfolio yield shows a significant positive relationship with the Grameen model and average loan size but is negatively related to debt. The operating self-sufficiency exhibits a significant positive relationship with the Grameen model and average loan size but a negative relationship with quasi-equity, debt, and philanthropic funds. These results suggest that capital structure has a significant impact on the returns of MFIs, which is aligned with the findings of Bogan (2012) and Islam and Nasreen (2018). Finally, the loan-to-deposit ratio shows a statistically significant negative relationship with the Grameen Model but a positive relationship with quasi-equity and philanthropic funds. These results suggest that capital structure significantly impacts the risk of MFIs, which is aligned with the findings of Dang et

al. (2023). However, quasi-equity and philanthropic funds remain insignificant in relation to portfolio yield, indicating that capital structure has no impact on MFIs return (aligned with Geresem & Michael, 2021). Additionally, the loan-to-deposit ratio remains insignificant with debt and average loan size, indicating that capital structure has no impact on the risk of MFIs, which is aligned with the findings of Dabi et al. (2023) and Almansour et al. (2019). Lastly, the coefficients among the independent variables are less than 0.80, indicating little chance of multicollinearity problems (Hasan, Hossain, Islam, & Hasan, 2023). Here, the mean value of the variance inflation factor (VIF) is 1.93, which is less than 10, indicating no multicollinearity problem among the independent variables (Hasan, Tawfiq, Hasan & Islam, 2024b).

Table 3: Correlation Matrix

Variables Name	PY	OSS	LDR	GM	QE	DE	PF	ALS	VIF
Portfolio Yield (PY)	1.0000								-
Operating Self Sufficiency (OSS)	0.3161***	1.0000							-
Loan to Deposit Ratio (LDR)	-0.1352***	-0.1367***	1.0000						
Grameen Model (GM)	0.2138***	0.1980***	-0.2955***	1.0000					2.47
Quasi Equity (QE)	-0.0259	-0.1003**	0.1837***	0.3323***	1.0000				1.3
Debt (DE)	-0.1112**	-0.1841*	0.0613	0.3485***	0.2585***	1.0000			1.3
Philanthropic Fund (PF)	0.0257	-0.0738*	0.0829*	0.2096***	0.2141***	0.2965***	1.0000		1.27
Average Loan Size (ALS)	0.2304*	0.0839*	-0.0300	0.7595*	0.4760*	0.4374*	0.4263*	1.0000	3.33
Mean VIF									1.93

***, **, and * indicate the level of significance at 0.001, 0.01, and 0.05, respectively; t statistics are enclosed in parentheses

Notes: This table shows the Pearson correlation matrix for the impact of capital structure on risk and returns measures of microfinance institutions. Here, portfolio yield and operating self-sufficiency were employed as return measures, the loan-to-deposit ratio was considered as risk measures, the Grameen model, quasi-equity, debt and philanthropic fund were considered as capital structure parameters and average loan size used as control variables from the period of 2012 to 2023 for 80 MFIs in Bangladesh.

The Feasible Generalized Least Squares (FGLS) model has been chosen for panel regression analysis considering the presence of autocorrelation and cross-sectional correlation following previous authors Dhiab (2021); Hasan and Hasan (2024). The FGLS model's overall results show that capital structure components significantly impact the returns and risk of micro-finance institutions (Table 4).

Table 4: Results of impact of capital structure on risk and returns of MFIs using Feasible Generalized Least Square (FGLS) method

Variables (T-stat)	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3
	Portfolio Yield (T-stat)	Operating Self Sufficiency (T-Stat)	Loan to Deposit Ratio (T-stat)
Grameen Model	0.1110 (0.98)	2.6180*** (3.87)	-0.4840*** (-15.43)
Quasi Equity	-0.4240** (-2.89)	-2.3100* (-2.05)	0.2880*** (6.59)
Debt	-0.7100*** (-4.61)	-2.3640* (-2.17)	0.1240* (2.36)
Philanthropic Fund	-0.2100* (-2.25)	-0.0006 (-0.82)	0.0771 (1.65)
Average Loan Size	1.9200*** (4.44)	1.1380 (0.54)	0.4510*** (3.98)
Constant	18.95*** (34.35)	105.6*** (37.75)	3.362*** (17.43)
Wald Chi ²	82.40***	34.35***	664.12***
No. of Obs.	732	732	732

***, **, and * indicate the level of significance at 0.001, 0.01, and 0.05, respectively; t statistics are enclosed in parentheses.

Notes: The table represents the result of the FGLS model of panel data analysis, examining two return-measuring variables (portfolio yield and operating self-sufficiency) and one risk-measuring variable (loan to deposit ratio) on the capital structure (i.e. grameen model, quasi-equity, debt and philanthropic funds) of Microfinance Institutions in Bangladesh for the period of 2012 to 2023. Here, the average loan size is used as a control variable.

The coefficient of portfolio yield and operating self-sufficiency exhibit that overall capital structure has a statistically significant impact on the returns of MFIs, which supports hypothesis *H1* (Model 1 and Model 2 of Table 4). The results show that portfolio yield has a statistically significant and negative relationship with quasi-equity ($\beta = -0.4240$, $P < 0.01$), debt ($\beta = -0.71$, $P < 0.001$) and philanthropic funds ($\beta = -0.21$, $P < 0.05$). Additionally, results show that operating self-sufficiency has a statistically significant positive relationship with the Grameen model ($\beta = 2.6180$, $P < 0.001$) but have a significant and negative relationship with the quasi-equity ($\beta = -2.31$, $P < 0.05$) and debt ($\beta = -2.3640$, $P < 0.05$). Here, portfolio yield has no statistically significant relationship with the Grameen model and operating self-sufficiency remains insignificant with philanthropic funds.

Model 3 of Table 4 exhibits that the coefficients of capital structure components have a statistically significant impact on risk measure, the loan-to-deposit ratio of MFIs, which supports hypothesis *H2*. The results show that loan to deposit ratio has a statistically significant positive relationship with quasi-equity ($\beta = 0.2880$, $P < 0.001$), debt ($\beta = 0.1240$, $P < 0.05$) and average loan size ($\beta = 0.4510$, $P < 0.001$). Moreover, loan to deposit has a significant negative relationship with the Grameen model ($\beta = -0.4840$, $P < 0.001$), but remains insignificant with philanthropic funds ($\beta = 0.0771$, $P > 0.05$).

The robustness of the results of the FGLS regression (Table 4) has been checked by conducting a random effect model following the Hausman test and the Breusch Pagan Lagrange Multiplier test, the random effect model. The random effects model results confirm a significant relationship between capital structure components and MFIs' returns and risk measures, aligning with the FGLS model findings and reinforcing their validity (Table 5).

Table 5: Results of impact of capital structure on risk and returns of MFIs using Random Effect Model

Variables	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3
	Portfolio Yield (T-stat)	Operating Self Sufficiency (T-Stat)	Loan to Deposit Ratio (T-stat)
Grameen Model	0.150 (1.24)	2.204*** (3.71)	-0.388*** (-9.96)
Quasi Equity	-0.2190* (-2.27)	-1.412* (-2.21)	0.0479* (2.14)
Debt	-0.654*** (-5.69)	-3.135*** (-5.54)	0.1019* (2.33)
Philanthropic Fund	-0.315** (-2.64)	-0.237 (-0.40)	-0.0047 (-0.12)
Average Loan Size	1.184*** (3.75)	1.656 (1.09)	1.326*** (12.91)
Constant	19.67*** (35.53)	104.9*** (47.27)	2.762*** (12.29)
Wald Chi ²	142.64***	67.09***	140.26***
R ²	0.3171	0.3298	0.1195
No. of Obs.	732	732	732

***, **, and * indicate the level of significance at 0.001, 0.01, and 0.05, respectively; t statistics are enclosed in parentheses.

Notes: The table represents the result of the random effect model of panel data analysis, examining two return-measuring variables and one risk-measuring variable on the capital structure of MFIs in Bangladesh for the period of 2012 to 2023.

DISCUSSIONS

The regression analysis shows that capital structure significantly impacts both the return and the risk of the MFIs in Bangladesh. From the perspective of MFI returns, the findings show that the coefficient of the Grameen model has a statistically significant and positive relationship with operating self-sufficiency, indicating that the inclusion of the Grameen model in capital structure increases the returns of MFIs, which is aligned with the findings of Parvin et al. (2020), Hăpău (2018) and Rutanga et al. (2021). This finding indicates that including the client's savings and cumulative surplus in capital structure helps to increase the returns through low-cost funding sources, reducing reliance on expensive external financing, and improving financial sustainability. However, the Grameen model indicates no significant impact on portfolio yield, which is aligned with the findings of Geresem and Michael (2021).

In the context of quasi-equity, findings show that it has a significant negative relationship with the returns measures like portfolio yield and operating self-sufficiency. This indicates the inclusion of quasi-equity in capital structure increases the cost of capital, which decreases the returns of MFIs, which is supported by Parvin et al. (2020) and Hoque et al. (2011). Similar to quasi-equity, debt exhibits a significant negative relation with return measures, indicating that an increase of debt in capital structure increases interest and financing costs, which decreases the MFIs' return (in line with findings of Sekabira's, 2013 and Rutanga et al., 2021). Subsequently, philanthropic funds show a significant negative relationship with portfolio yield, indicating that an increase in capital structure shows MFIs mostly rely on donations, and that hampers their self-fund operations which decreases the portfolio yield (aligned with Tchuigoua, 2015; Bogan, 2012; and Sekabira,2013).

In the case of the risk of MFIs, the Grameen model shows a significant negative relationship with the loan-to-deposit ratio, indicating that when the MFIs operate with client's savings and surplus as capital, they face lower risk. The quasi-equity and debt show a significant positive relationship with the loan-to-deposit ratio, indicating that the increase of quasi-equity and debt in capital structure increases its liquidity and default risk, making MFIs more risky, which is similar to the findings of Dang et al. (2023). It indicates that including quasi-equity and debt in capital structure generates more financing costs and interest, reducing the MFIs' profits and increasing overall MFIs' risk. Additionally, philanthropic funds have no impact on the risk of MFIs, which is consistent with the outcomes of Debi et al. (2023) and Almansour et al. (2019). Furthermore, the average loan size has a significant positive

relationship with portfolio yield and loan-to-deposit ratio, indicating that an average loan size increases both returns and risk.

CONCLUSION

This study aims to measure the impact of capital structures of MFIs like the Grameen model, quasi-equity, debt, and philanthropic funds on the risk measured by loan-to-deposit ratio and return measured by portfolio yield and operating self-sufficiency. For this purpose, data from 61 Bangladeshi MFIs have been collected from 2012 to 2023. The FGLS and the random effect models of panel data analysis are utilized here to reach the research objective. Mixed evidence has been identified regarding the influence of the capital structure on risk and return of MFIs.

The study's findings show that the Grameen model helps increase MFI return by increasing the operating self-sufficiency, though it remains insignificant with portfolio yield. The quasi-equity and debt explain that returns are negatively correlated with capital structure. The findings suggest that higher reliance on quasi-equity and debt in the capital structure reduces MFIs' returns, likely due to increased financial costs, interest obligations, and operational inefficiencies. The philanthropic fund has a significant negative relation with portfolio yield, indicating that increased reliance on donations or grants reduces MFIs' financial performance, possibly due to lower pressure for profitability and inefficiencies in fund utilization. Regarding risk, the quasi-equity and debt exhibit a significant positive relationship with the loan-to-deposit ratio, suggesting that higher reliance on these funding sources increases MFIs' financial risk by raising leverage and potential repayment obligations. However, the Grameen model has a significant negative relation with the loan-to-deposit ratio, which implies that MFIs following this model rely more on client savings and internal funds rather than external borrowing, leading to lower leverage and reduced financial risk. Moreover, the average loan size shows a significant positive relationship with both risk and returns measures of MFIs.

The results show that while reliance on debt and quasi-equity lowers returns because of greater financial expenses, the Grameen model improves operating self-sufficiency and hence improves financial sustainability. For MFIs that rely on donations, the detrimental effect of philanthropic contributions on portfolio yield highlights sustainability issues. Furthermore, the requirement for balanced loan portfolio management is highlighted by the fact that greater loan sizes raise both risk and rewards. In order to balance risk management, social impact,

and financial viability, MFIs must generally implement an ideal capital structure. Financial patrons and funders (including banks, influence financial providers, and developers) can utilize the exploration discoveries to evaluate the risk-return profiles of MFIs in Bangladesh.

This study possesses specific limitations that offer avenues for future research. First, the study primarily concentrates on Bangladeshi MFIs, hence constraining the applicability of the results to other locations with distinct legislative and financial contexts. Second, the studies may broaden the analysis to a cross-national context for enhanced insights. The analysis predominantly utilizes annual data, which may fail to reflect short-term variations in risk and return. Future research may employ higher-frequency data, such as quarterly or monthly observations, to improve precision. Third, although the study analyzes essential components of capital structure, it neglects to address the impact of developing financial innovations, such as digital finance and impact investments, which could affect MFI performance. Future study may investigate the influence of these developments on the risk-return profiles of microfinance institutions (MFIs)

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